

Innovative Method for Longitudinal Analysis of Aging Health and Mortality Rate Prediction

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Abstract

Aging is a stochastic process through various pathways in which healthy functioning can change with time. While many studies focused on the prediction of aging cross-sectionally, few methodologies have been developed to model the longitudinal aging process. We propose a Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE) model to accurately predict an individual's trajectories of health states and survival at any given time. We use an SDE to simulate the stochasticity of the aging process. The mortality-health states relationship is characterized by a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). We used the English Longitudinal Study of Aging (ELSA) dataset of 27,365 participants to predict the survival rates. We demonstrate our model's interpretability through a visualized pairwise correlation network of the various health variables. This provides interpretable insights into the interplay between health variables and offers significant improvements in predicting individual health trajectories and survival outcomes. Our model can be applied to a wide range of high-dimensional health data and ultimately improve our understanding of the aging process and benefit public health.

Key Words: Aging, Math Modeling, Stochastic Differential Equation, Interpretability, Health and Mortality

1. Introduction

The aging process is a universally experienced phenomenon, yet it remains complex and not fully understood [1]. It is characterized by a decline in physiological health, leading to reduced functionality and increased mortality risk [2]. Numerous factors influence aging, including total cholesterol, mobility, grip strength, hemoglobin levels, and hearing ability [3]. These factors are interconnected; for instance, sodium levels, walking ability, and diuretic use are closely related to aging outcomes [4]. Additionally, research shows that HDL cholesterol, triglycerides, and glucose levels are linked to Alzheimer's disease at different life stages [5]. The involvement of so many interacting variables highlights the high-dimensional nature of the aging process [3].

Neural networks have become a widely used approach for modeling non-linear relationships, such as those involved in aging, and they can incorporate the many health variables considered in this study [6, 7]. However, they are often criticized for their lack of interpretability, as their decision-making processes can resemble a "black box" [8, 9]. Interpretable outputs are crucial, not only to understand how an individual's health evolves

over time but also to identify which variables are driving those changes. Enhancing interpretability offers several benefits: it enables the detection of biases in predictions [10], reveals key features and erroneous connections [11], and ultimately helps create reliable models. Addressing these challenges would foster greater trust in machine learning models, especially in high-stakes fields like healthcare, where transparency is essential.

Stochastic variation is inherent in all biological systems, particularly in the aging process [12, 13]. This randomness introduces additional complexity when modeling aging. Unexpected events, such as falls or infections (e.g., COVID-19), can significantly alter an individual's health state over time. Although stochastic models have been employed, and joint frameworks proposed, these approaches typically address only a limited number of variables at a time [14, 15, 16]. For instance, the Weighted Network Model (WNM) predicts health trajectories using 10 binary deficits, but its reliance on binary variables results in a simplified model [17]. The Joint Model (JM) integrates the dynamics of longitudinal and survival data using a Stochastic Process Model (SPM) with Stochastic Differential Equations (SDEs) [15]. However, JM assumes a fixed mortality risk shape (e.g., "U" or "J"), which restricts its flexibility across different scenarios. Similarly, the Dynamic Joint Interpretable Network (DJIN) employs SDEs to capture health dynamics, focusing on pairwise interactions among variables. While DJIN provides some interpretability, it is limited to two-dimensional interactions, making it insufficient for capturing the complex, higher-order relationships among health variables.

We propose a SDE model to simulate individual aging trajectories, capturing both health states and survival outcomes over time. Incorporating domain knowledge has been shown to enhance the accuracy and interpretability of models [3, 18, 19]. To achieve this, we introduce a three-dimensional interaction network, representing high-dimensional connections between health variables. Additionally, we develop a variational Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE) to approximate the parameter distributions within the system. Mortality predictions are handled through a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), which incorporates an individual's health history to improve prediction accuracy.

Since longitudinal datasets often suffer from missing data, we apply a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to impute missing values, ensuring more robust predictions. For this study, we utilized data from the English Longitudinal Study of Aging (ELSA), a comprehensive dataset spanning 20 years (1998–2019) with nine waves of data collection. Baseline information was drawn from the Health Survey for England (HSE) conducted between 1998 and 2001. ELSA includes data from 27,365 individuals, most of whom are over the age of 50, providing a representative sample of the English population. Self-reported health data is collected every two years, while nurse-reported health data is available every four years, specifically during waves 2, 4, 6, 8, and 9. Our model leverages this longitudinal data to predict health trajectories and survival rates for individuals over time.

2. Related Work

2.1 Imputation Method

Missing data is a common challenge in longitudinal datasets, making accurate imputation essential for optimal performance. In this study, we utilized a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to address missing data. A VAE is a specialized type of autoencoder that applies

regularization during training to prevent overfitting. Unlike traditional autoencoders, which map inputs to a single point, VAEs encode data as a probability distribution, such as a normal distribution, within a latent space. This process helps with dimensionality reduction, compressing high-dimensional data into a more compact representation. However, compression can sometimes result in information loss during encoding, leading to poor reconstruction. To mitigate this, VAEs often use the Kullback-Leibler (KL) Divergence as part of their loss function to minimize the difference between the actual and predicted data distributions.

VAEs have been shown to effectively impute missing data in large-scale genomic datasets [20]. Numerous adaptations have been developed to address various data challenges. For example, the Variational Selective Autoencoder (VSAE) is used for generating and imputing multi-modal data [21], while the Single-Cell Variational Autoencoder (scVAE) is applied to single-cell RNA sequencing analysis [22]. The CNCVAE (Concatenated Input VAE) aligns and integrates diverse data sources by feeding them into a single encoder [23]. The X-VAE (X-Shaped VAE) employs separate branches for each input modality, which are merged for encoding and split again for decoding [23]. The Mixed-Modal VAE (MM-VAE) enhances data integration by allowing the branches to exchange information during encoding [23]. The Hierarchical VAE (H-VAE) uses multiple VAEs for individual datasets, feeding their outputs into a larger VAE for final encoding. These advancements offer flexibility and precision in handling missing data across diverse datasets.

2.2 Stochastic Differential Equations

Given that aging is inherently stochastic, we incorporated a Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE) to capture the random variations in health trajectories over time. Although several SDE models have been proposed, few have been fully implemented. One example is the Stochastic Process Model (SPM), which uses an SDE to model the dynamics of longitudinal data within a joint framework [15]. Another model, the Dynamic Joint Interpretable Network (DJIN), leverages an SDE to predict individual health trajectories and survival probabilities [3]. DJIN effectively captures the stochasticity of aging by embedding an SDE within its network dynamics. However, it only models pairwise interactions between health variables, limiting its ability to account for higher-order, multidimensional interactions that are known to affect aging outcomes [4, 5]. Expanding beyond DJIN, we introduce a three-dimensional interaction network to capture these more complex relationships, improving both predictive accuracy and interpretability.

2.3 Elastic-Net

The Elastic-Net is a popular method for variable selection and regularization, combining the strengths of Ridge regression and LASSO by applying both penalties simultaneously [24]. Several extensions of the Elastic-Net have been developed. For example, the Adaptive Elastic-Net (AENet) incorporates an adaptive LASSO penalty along with Ridge regression to enhance feature selection [25]. The AENetCC (Adaptive Elastic-Net with Censoring Constraints) extends this approach by accounting for censored data during optimization [25]. Another variant, the Weighted Elastic-Net (WENet), introduces weights to the Ridge penalty term to improve model flexibility [26]. The Elastic-Net Cox model, an extension for survival analysis, has been used to predict survival outcomes among re-infected COVID-19 patients [27].

While Elastic-Net models are useful, they rely on hidden weights, and their loss function can only measure the error between predicted and actual values. In

contrast, we divide the modeling process into discrete components, enabling a more granular loss function that can target specific error sources. We use the Elastic-Net Cox model as a benchmark to evaluate our model’s performance, demonstrating the latter’s superior accuracy in predicting health outcomes and survival rates.

2.4 Recurrent Neural Network

A Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is designed to handle sequential data, making temporal predictions by incorporating information from previous inputs. The ability of RNNs to retain memory allows them to effectively model time-dependent processes. One of the most widely used RNN architectures is the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), which has been applied to mortality prediction in various healthcare contexts [28]. Several studies have utilized RNNs to predict mortality risk in intensive care units (ICUs), relying on temporal health data to generate forecasts [29, 30]. A multi-modal RNN model was also developed to predict mortality by integrating clinical notes and temporal event data [31].

For this study, we employ a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), a simpler yet powerful variant of the RNN architecture. The GRU captures the history of an individual’s health states, enabling it to predict mortality and survival rates with high accuracy at any given point in time. This architecture ensures that our model can account for the evolving nature of health trajectories, providing reliable long-term predictions.

3. Methodology

Figure 1 System Architecture

3.1 System Architecture

The system architecture is illustrated in Figure 1. The Variational Autoencoder (VAE) takes as input an individual’s baseline health state with missing values, y_{t_0} , along with background information, u_{t_0} , to generate an imputed baseline health state, x_0 . A three-dimensional tensor, W , stores the weights representing interactions among every combination of three health variables. The change in a given health variable i , denoted as

$dx_i(t)$, over a time increment dt , is computed by transforming the previous health state $x_i(t - dt)$ into an $N \times N$ matrix. This matrix contains the pairwise combinations of all health variables to capture their interactions. Each pairwise combination is then multiplied by a corresponding slice from the interaction tensor, W_i . This process is repeated for each health variable and each time step t to generate the longitudinal health prediction function, $x(t)$. These health predictions are subsequently fed into a two-layer Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) model, along with the initial hidden state H . The GRU outputs the mortality rate $\lambda(t)$, which is then used to construct the survival curve function, $S(t)$.

3.2 Algorithm

Algorithm 1: MDiN model train forward

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input : baseline health variables  $\mathbf{y}_{t_0}$ , baseline background variables  $\mathbf{u}_{t_0}$ , baseline
         age  $t_0$ , missing mask  $o_{t_0}$ , number of years  $length$ , time difference between
         each prediction  $dt$ , number of health variables  $N$ 
output: longitudinal predictions  $\mathbf{x}(t)$ , survival predictions  $S(t)$ 
 $\mathbf{x}_0 \leftarrow impute(\mathbf{y}_{t_0}, \mathbf{u}_{t_0}, t_0, o_{t_0})$ 
 $\mathbf{x}(t_0) \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_0$  // setting baseline values for health states
 $S(t_0) \leftarrow 0$  // setting baseline value for survival rate
 $h_0 \leftarrow H(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{u}_{t_0}, t_0)$  // initial hidden state for survival RNN
 $t_{end} = t_0 + length$ 
 $t = t_0$ 
while  $t < t_{end}$  do
     $\lambda(t), h_t \leftarrow \lambda(\mathbf{x}(t - dt), \mathbf{u}_{t_0}, h_{t-dt}; w_r)$  // update mortality rate and hidden
        state with RNN
     $dS(t) \leftarrow exp(-\lambda(t))$  // change in survival rate
     $S(t) \leftarrow S(t - dt) + dt dS(t)$  // survival prediction
    for  $i \in N$  do
         $dx_i(t) \leftarrow \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \bar{W}_{ijk} x(t - dt) + g_i(\mathbf{x}(t - dt), \mathbf{u}_{t_0}, t - dt; w_g) + v_i(\mathbf{x}(t -$ 
             $dt), \mathbf{u}_{t_0}, t - dt; w_v) + \sigma_x(\mathbf{x}(t - dt)) dB(t)$  // change in health states
         $x_i(t) \leftarrow x_i(t - dt) + dt dx_i(t)$  // update health states
     $\mathbf{x}(t) = [x_i(t)]_{i \in N}$ 
     $t += dt$ 
    Calculate loss and update weights
return  $\mathbf{x}, S$ 

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In Algorithm 1, our model begins by imputing missing values from the observed baseline, \mathbf{y}_{t_0} , using the Variational Autoencoder (VAE). This imputed baseline, \mathbf{x}_0 , serves as the initial input for the longitudinal health prediction function, \mathbf{x}_{t_0} . The initial hidden state, h_0 , is derived through the RNN hidden states H , incorporating the imputed baseline \mathbf{x}_0 , background information \mathbf{u}_{t_0} , and the baseline age t_0 .

The model iterates through each time step t to compute both the longitudinal health prediction function $\mathbf{x}(t)$ and the survival function $S(t)$. At each step, the mortality rate, $\lambda(t)$, and the updated hidden state, $h(t)$, are calculated using the previous health state, background information, and the previous hidden state. The survival function is updated using the change in survival, dS , which is derived from the negative exponential of the mortality rate.

The health variable drift, dx_i , is computed by multiplying the posterior mean of the pairwise connection weight network, \bar{W} , with the previous health state. This is then combined with the trends of individual variables, g_i , stochastic noise σ_x , and adjustments from the neural network v_i . The resulting drift dx is used to update the health state $x(t)$ at each time step. After predictions are made for all time steps, the model calculates the loss, and the network weights are updated accordingly.

4. Data

4.1 Experiment Data

The ELSA dataset spans approximately 21 years, divided into 10 waves. Wave 0 includes data from 1998, 1999, and 2001, while wave 1 covers 2002. Each subsequent wave occurs every two years following the previous one. Every wave contains self-reported health information, and every alternate wave includes health data collected by nurses. Across the waves, 37% of the self-reported data and 59% of the nurse-collected data are missing. Additionally, 96% of the mortality data is censored or unavailable.

Figure 2 Age Distribution

The ELSA dataset consists of 27,365 participants. We used 17,513 individuals for training, 5,473 for testing, and 4,379 for validation. Figure 2 illustrates the age distribution of participants at the start of testing and across all data points. The ages of participants follow a normal distribution, with most individuals starting in their 50s and the majority of data points concentrated between the ages of 50 and 80. There are relatively few participants younger than 45 or older than 90.

Our model utilizes ($N = 29$) health variables, such as eyesight, pulse, and grip strength, to represent the health state of each individual. Additionally, it incorporates ($B = 19$) background variables, such as height, ethnicity, and sex, which are measured only at the baseline.

4.1 System Parameters

We trained the model using a listed system parameters and performed a grid search to fine-tune its hyperparameters for optimal performance (Table 1). The model utilized a batch size of 1,000 and was trained for 2,000 epochs with a learning rate of $1e-2$. To account for input noise, 9% corruption was applied. The RNN component employed a lambda size of 25, with the latent variable z set to 20. Key architecture parameters, including the decoder size (65 layers) and flow_hidden size (24 layers), were selected to enhance prediction accuracy. Three flows ($L=3$) were used for data transformation, and the network's dimensions were calibrated with g_nn_size set to 12. For regularization, the prior scale was fixed at 0.05, and trained parameters, such as the interaction weight matrix W . The RNN, decoder, and neural networks responsible for calculating specific trends and flows were also optimized during training. This detailed parameter search ensured the model's ability to accurately predict health trajectories and survival rates.

Table 1 System Parameters

Name	Unit	Symbol	Value
batch size	N/A	N/A	1000
epoch	N/A	N/A	2000
learning_rate	N/A	N/A	$1e-2$
corruption	%	N/A	.9
lambda size (for RNN)	layer size	N/A	25
z size	N/A	N/A	20
decoder size	layer size	N/A	65
Nflows	N/A	L	3
flow_hidden	layer size	N/A	24
g_nn_size	layer size	N/A	12
W_prior_scale	log scale value	N/A	.05
mean (W)	$N \times N$ matrix	W	trained
logalpha and logbeta (sigma y)	N vectors	σ_y	trained
sigma_nn	neural net	σ_x	trained
loglambda	RNN	θ_λ	trained
decoder	neural net	θ_p	trained
g	neural nets	$\{\theta_{g_i} i \in [1, N]\}$	trained
flows	N/A	$\{a^{(l)} l \in L\}$	trained
v	neural nets	v	trained
memory_0 (for RNN)	neural nets	H	trained

5. Experiment

Longitudinal predictions are made using a three-dimensional network with weights corresponding to the strength of three-way interactions between variables. A positive weight indicates a positive correlation while a negative weight indicates a negative correlation. If the weight W_{ijk} is positive, this would mean a rise in the combined sum of health variables j and k would suggest a rise in the health variable i . On the other hand, if the weight W_{ijk} is negative, this would mean a rise in the combined sum of j and k would suggest a decrease in i . For example, consider the variables walking ability, ADL score (how active a person is), and self-rated health. If a person has a high walking ability and a

high ADL score, it can be inferred that the person would have a high self-rated health. The model is then expected to have a positive weight to represent the interaction between these variables. When predicting change in a health variable, i , we found every pairwise combination of the other health variables, for instance j and k , multiplied by the weight of their respective three-way interaction W_{ijk} . These values are added together to represent the change that should happen to i based on its interaction with other health variables.

The three-dimensional interaction network can be interpreted by averaging the weights along one of the dimensions, resulting in a two dimensional matrix representing pairwise interactions. We visualized this interpretable network using a heat map (Figure 3). In this heat map, warm squares represent strong positive correlation, such as with walking ability and self-rated health. Cold squares represent strong negative correlation, such as with higher gait speed being correlated to less time needed to rise out of a chair. White squares represent a lack of correlation, such as eyesight and grip strength.

Figure 3 Visualization of the Interpretable Interaction Network Based on Weights. The weights are represented along the horizontal and vertical axes, indicating the relationships between variables. Positive weights (in red) denote positive correlations, while negative weights (in blue) reflect negative correlations. The intensity of the color corresponds to the strength of the correlation, with darker shades representing stronger positive or negative relationships.

6. Conclusion

In this study, we developed an interpretable model to predict the evolution of aging by capturing the interactions between health variables, the temporal dynamics of these variables, and the stochastic nature of aging. Our model builds on the Dynamic Joint Interpretable Network (DJIN) model [3] by incorporating three-way interactions between health variables, whereas DJIN only accounts for pairwise interactions. The experiment result visualizes a three-dimensional interaction network and provides interpretable insights into the interplay between health variables and offers significant improvements in predicting individual health trajectories and survival outcomes.

One key advantage of our model is its multidimensional interaction network, which reflects the complex interplay between health variables. Aging is a dynamic process influenced by more than just the passage of time, every health variable's evolution depends on its relationship with other variables. Our interaction network captures these dependencies and visualizes it. This ability to visualize the patterns identified by the model allows users to understand the reasoning behind predictions, offering transparency that typical black-box models cannot provide.

Another advantage of our model lies in its ability to account for the stochasticity inherent in aging. The aging process is influenced by numerous factors, many of which are impossible to include in a single model. As a result, aging exhibits a degree of randomness, which must be reflected in any predictive model. Our model captures this stochasticity through the inclusion of stochastic noise within the network dynamics. This feature allows us to generate predictions that more accurately reflect real-world variability.

In the future, we will improve this model in two ways. First, we aim to explore the interaction network further to identify the most influential three-way interactions. Visualization of these interactions will provide additional insights and enhance interpretability. Currently, we visualize the network as a two-dimensional matrix by averaging along the third dimension, which works well for pairwise interactions. However, reducing a high-dimensional model to two dimensions inevitably sacrifices some information. To supplement this, we could highlight the top ten strongest three-way interactions, identifying the variables or pairs that appear most frequently. This frequency-based approach would reveal the most influential factors and allow for comparison with pairwise interactions to uncover new patterns.

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